

PROMOTING CRITICAL THINKING IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING PROBLEM-SOLVING USING DYNAMIC SIMULATION

S.M. Cheah, and S.T. Phua

Singapore Polytechnic, Singapore

smcheah@sp.edu.sg

Abstract

In chemical engineering, critical thinking skills are crucial in troubleshooting plant problems or making design changes, as one must think through the impact of making a change in one parameter (such as temperature) on other parameters (pressure, flow rate, composition, level, etc). Educators in chemical engineering often face the challenge of inculcating critical thinking skills among students in dealing with problems that involve many process variables that are often inter-related.

One way to stimulate critical thinking is through classroom activities that actively engage the students. Various strategies for actively engaging students to promote better learning are available and well documented. One of the most common strategies involves dividing students into smaller groups and engaging them in small group activities. Various techniques have been introduced, including Think-Pair-Share, Syndicates, Role Play, etc. Technologies are often employed to facilitate such learning process.

This paper focuses on using dynamic simulation, a software tool for the training of engineering technicians in the chemical process industries, to actively engage students in critical thinking, using a core chemical engineering module. Firstly, it briefly discusses the importance of critical thinking, in the context of chemical engineering education, followed by a brief discussion of dynamic simulation. The selection of the chosen module and implementation methodology is then briefly discussed. It then highlights the challenges faced in dealing with large number of students followed by discussion on the benefits that dynamic simulation tools offers as reported by survey results from students. Lastly it addresses the lessons learnt by the team and outlined some future plans.

Keywords: *Dynamic simulation, chemical engineering, active learning, critical thinking*

Introduction

A particular challenge facing educators in chemical engineering is the inter-relatedness of various process variables. A typical chemical plant is made up of a number of unit operations in which various process parameters such as pressure, flow rate, composition, level, etc are being monitored and controlled. Often changes in one variable will have significant impact on other variables throughout the plant. Engineers and operators therefore need to have a thorough understanding of the inter-relatedness of the various variables to perform their tasks in a safe and efficient manner. This requires critical thinking skills, which are important attributes desired in students from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering. The team felt that one way to stimulate critical thinking is through classroom activities that promote active learning among students. One of the approaches taken is through the use of dynamic simulation.

As critical thinking and simulation are broad topics open to different interpretations by different persons, we will firstly start with some working definitions to put the entire work as presented in this paper into its proper context.

Critical Thinking in Context

The importance of critical thinking in engineering education had been well covered in the literature. Moore (2006) defined critical thinking as:

A deliberate meta-cognitive (*thinking about thinking*) and cognitive (*thinking*) act whereby a person reflects on the quality of the reasoning process simultaneously while reasoning to a conclusion. The thinker has two equally important goals: coming to a solution and improving the way she or he reasons. (Italics in original)

Carroll (2004) noted that:

The goal of thinking critically is simple: to guarantee, as far as possible, that one's beliefs and actions are justifiable and can withstand the test of rational analysis.

In a more layperson interpretation, critical thinking may consist of seeing both sides of an issue, being open to new evidence that disconfirms an original idea, reasoning dispassionately, demanding that claims be backed by evidence, deducing and inferring conclusions from available facts, solving problems, and so forth. There are specific types of critical thinking that are characteristic of different subject matter, for example, in the chemical processing industry, we often refer to critical thinking “thinking like a chemical engineer”. But what does “thinking like a chemical engineer” actually mean?

In this paper, we are specifically interested in the following aspects of critical thinking:

- Ability to compare and contrast the differences in various process variables (temperature, level, pressure, flow rate, composition) in a chemical process plant resulting from a disturbance in stable operating condition or due to equipment malfunction
- Ability to make inferences and interpretations from the above using relevant theories and concepts
- Ability to link together the various observed phenomena and offer plausible explanations of what had happened in the plant

From the onset, we decided that the teaching of critical thinking must be contextualized to the intended learning outcome. As noted by Willingham (2007), the processes of thinking are intertwined with the content of thought (that is, domain knowledge). Thus, if you remind a student to “look at an issue from multiple perspectives” often enough, he will learn that he ought to do so, but if he doesn’t know much about an issue, he *can’t* think about it from multiple perspectives. You can teach students maxims about how they ought to think, but without background knowledge and practice, they probably will not be able to implement the advice they memorize. Just as it makes no sense to try to teach factual content without giving students opportunities to practice using it, it also makes no sense to try to teach critical thinking devoid of factual content.

Dynamic Simulation in Context

In a nutshell, simulation is the construction and use of a computer-based representation, or model, of some part of the real world as a substitute vehicle for experiment and behavior prediction. The central components of the simulation process are building the model (modeling) and running the model (i.e. the experiment). Broadly speaking, two types of simulation can be discerned, namely “static” (or steady state) simulation and dynamic simulation. By steady state simulation we mean that the modeled process is solved only for a specific set of operating conditions. This is like a snapshot of the process or operation. Any change in the operating conditions, requires re-solving the model. After converging, the model should predict where the process will settle. On the other hand, dynamic

modeling will provide us with information about the process or operation over time. All variables are being “solved” at each time step and at any specific time we can monitor the operating conditions. Compared to the steady state “snapshot” equivalent, the dynamic modeling is more of a movie than a single picture.

Luyben (2002) described the factors driving the increased popularity of dynamic simulation in the chemical processing industry, such as increased plant complexity, increasing product yield and suppressing of environmentally unfriendly by-products.

Dynamic simulation used to be the privileges of large corporations and universities with generous research fundings. Womack (1986) for example, reported their use in Mobil Research & Development Corporation. Typical uses include review of new design and control strategy, modeling transient behavior, troubleshooting and operator training. With technological advances that resulted in declining manufacturing cost and increasing computing power, dynamic simulation tools are now becoming affordable to educational institutions in general. The usage here is primarily for fundamental research at the molecular level, as well as to facilitate understanding of basic chemical engineering fundamentals. Bell and Fogler (1997), Eich-Sollner et al (1997), Gossage et al (2001) provided a detailed discussion on the use of computer simulations in the context of chemical engineering education.

In dynamic simulation, natural and chemical phenomena are expressed with algebraic and differential equations based on engineering principles. The mathematical models created are used for analysing how process behaviour varies with time. For the typical case of a process industry, we describe/model the plant subunits and their regulatory control. The relevant equations are solved repeatedly in the time domain and the values of temperature, pressure, flow and composition as well as the valve openings and the process control system output are calculated at every point of interest. Thus, the interactions between the process subunits can become obvious. Further, the process reaction to disturbances (such as feed variation, instruments failure or change of operation strategy) can be fully investigated (Hyperion Systems Engineering, 2006).

It is the effectiveness of using dynamic simulation as a vehicle for developing skill in critical thinking that is the specific focus of this work. The dynamic simulation package is the Process Fundamentals Unit-I and Unit-II from EnVision Systems Inc (<http://www.envisionsys.com/>), which is used for the training of process technicians and operators. The package consists of a series of fundamental simulation models for understanding of Process Dynamics, Equipment Principles, their Operations and Process Control.

Materials and Methods or Pedagogy

We decided to pilot the initiative with a module within the Diploma in Chemical Engineering. We adopted the activity design using the student-centered framework “Triangle of Course Design” by Felder and Brent (2003) as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Student-centred approach to curriculum design

The learning objectives obviously strive to achieve the outcomes as mentioned above. As for instructional methodology, we chose dynamic simulation as the instructional approach. As noted by Jonassen (2001):

Computers can most effectively support meaningful learning and knowledge construction in higher education as cognitive amplification tools for reflecting on what students have learned and what they know. Rather than using the power of computer technologies to disseminate information, they should be used in all subject domains as tools for engaging learners in reflective, critical thinking about the ideas they are studying.

The advantage of using dynamic simulation had been covered by various authors. For the intended learning outcomes of our case, this is aptly summarized by Gurmen et al (2003) who noted that:

Interactive computing can greatly facilitate the learning of troubleshooting skills because of the rapid feedback, the alternate pathways the student may progress and the multiple solutions they can generate. Complementary to the traditional classes, interactive computer modules enable the students to create various what-if scenarios and to concentrate on critical thinking.

The module chosen in a Year-2 module entitled *Heat Transfer & Equipment*. This module is chosen because of the importance of heat exchangers in chemical processing plants. Despite its ubiquity in a typical chemical plant, a heat exchanger never exists in isolation: it is always part of a larger plant, e.g.

providing reboil for a distillation column, cooling for a multi-stage compressor, preheat for a reactor, etc. Operational problems exchanger can therefore affect other equipment to which it is connected to. Given the importance of heat exchangers in plant operations, it is often a paradox that it was not given the due attention that it deserved. Hence a heat exchanger would be a good choice of equipment for our instructional design that is contextualized to attain the intended learning outcome.

Heat exchangers can be found in many of the modules in both Units in the Process Fundamentals package. The one chosen for this work is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Chemical plant for dynamic simulation

There are altogether 3 classes of students taking this module, making a total number of 55 students. We designed activities using the model for the students to work in groups of 4 or 5 using their laptops. For this work, we created five different simulation exercises for 5 groups of students from each class, so that there are some variations among different group of students. For good measure, we also included exercises whereby failure of other plant components occurred so that students can understand how that leads to problems in the heat exchanger.

The students are given 1 week to complete the exercise outside of the classroom. During the exercise, students are required to first note down the original state of relevant process variables. Then they are to proceed to initiate a change in a selected process parameter and monitor the changes in the entire plant (see Figure 3). They will then record down the process variables once again, and proceed to provide a critical analysis of the observation, and offer plausible explanation for the observed changes using engineering reasoning.

After the exercise, students are required to do a 10 minute presentation of their findings and analysis. In particular, the students are required to explain how operational difficulty affects the entire plant operation and how failure in one part of the equipment can affect the heat exchanger performance. As each group of

students is given different simulation exercise, through this sharing session, students are given an opportunity to acquire learning points from other groups.

Figure 3. Sample screen capture of simulation model

To value add on the time spent, the presentation provides an opportunity for the students to share learning points from other groups and to clarify doubts on result obtained.

At the end of presentation, a short survey is used to gauge the learning outcome of this activity. The survey consists of 4 questions and students are required to provide a response to each question using a 5-point scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

1. I am aware that overall performance is dependent on the proper workings of each component equipment in the plant.
2. I am aware of the interconnectedness of various process variables (e.g., temperature, pressure, flow, level, etc) in a typical chemical plant.
3. I am able to think more critically (e.g. analyze, make inferences and interpretations, etc) in attempting to account for the observed changes.
4. I have a more integrated view of chemical engineering (e.g. I am able to link together various concepts learnt in different modules).

Challenges Face

We struggled initially with ascertaining the effectiveness of dynamic simulation in helping us to achieve the intended learning outcomes. A somewhat dated but comprehensive study by De Jong and Van Joolingen (1998) noted that “the general conclusion that emerges from these studies is that there is no clear and univocal outcome in favor of simulations.” Hermann (2002) in particular pointed out the dearth of studies in this area:

Although, there are some learning and thinking tasks relevant for students within computer simulations which are closely related to skills in critical thinking, only very few studies dealing with critical thinking and computer simulations can be found.

This is somewhat ironic for the discipline of chemical engineering, as critical thinking skills had been mentioned in most, if not all, of chemical engineering curriculum in the university and polytechnic programs. A cursory search using the Internet on a chemical engineering program invariably will mention the need to develop critical thinking skills in students. In fact, critical thinking had been rated as the number two skill in the Occupational Information Network (O*NET) of the US Department of Labor. However, the limited papers that discussed this topic mainly focus on using dynamic simulation to develop the theoretical understanding of underlying chemical engineering principles in university undergraduates. On the other hand, one of the graduate attributes desired by the industry is critical thinking skills in process troubleshooting and problem solving. Even at the polytechnic level, much of our curriculum is geared towards university education, and hence many of the topics closely mirrored those taught in the universities, and as such, critical thinking skills are not explicitly taught, much less assessed. For this pilot exercise, we therefore settled on a simple survey to assess students’ receptiveness of the approach.

Operationally, the first problem we faced is that of large class sizes. Teaching of chemical engineering in the Singapore Polytechnic employs a variety of strategies: from lectures to a large group of students in a lecture theatre to small group activities in the laboratory. We first contemplated carrying out the activity during lecture for all students, each of them worked on the same problem on their own. However, having considered that some may just rely on their neighbor to run the simulation model and obtain the results without exercising their own efforts, we decided to try other approaches. Creating different activities for each student is obviously not possible, given the large numbers that we had to deal with. In the end, we decided to adopt the same arrangement as that for our laboratory activities as explained in the previous section.

Another equally important issue we faced is that of trying to introduce a new learning activity into an already-packed curriculum. A related question is whether this activity will form part of the assessment or not. In the end, the exercise is introduced as an additional activity that is not part of the module assessment. Students are required to complete the exercise on their own time outside the classroom. A short briefing was conducted to familiarize the students with the dynamic simulation software, and how to use its various functions.

Results and Discussion

Troubleshooting skills are an important component for a successful practicing chemical engineering technologist. They require strong critical thinking skills and an ability to make connections between various process variables observed. These skills allow them to troubleshoot problems, develop and implementation of an optimum solution. Although experience is an important aspect of troubleshooting, these skills can be introduced in the classroom to offer students a more realistic chemical engineering experience (Gephardt, 2005). It is the author's belief that students introduced to troubleshooting early are likely to integrate more critical and creative thinking into their problem solving.

The results of our simple survey students typically Agree (Score 4) or Strongly Agree (Score 5) to the 4 questions posed.

Table 1. Overall Score from Survey

Question	AVERAGE of 3 classes
1	4.28
2	4.20
3	3.98
4	4.07
Average	4.13

Figure 4 showed the response to Question 1. 96.30% of the students agreed or strongly agreed that through this exercise, they are aware that overall performance in a chemical plant is dependent on the proper workings of each component equipment in the plant.

Figure 4. Response to Question 1

Figure 5, the response to Question 2, showed that 94.44% of the students agreed or strongly agreed that through this exercise, they are aware of the interconnectedness of various process variables (e.g., temperature, pressure, flow, level, etc) in a typical chemical plant. Figure 6, the response to Question 3, showed that 81.48% of the students agreed or strongly agreed that through this exercise, they are able to think

more critically (e.g. analyse, make inferences and interpretations, etc) in attempting to account for the observed changes.

Figure 5. Response to Question 2

Figure 6. Response to Question 3

Lastly, as shown in Figure 7, 87.04% of the students agreed or strongly agreed that through this exercise, they have a more integrated view of chemical engineering (e.g. they are able to link together various concepts learnt in different modules).

Figure 7. Response to Question 4

It is evident from this simple survey that the area needing improvement is the students' ability to think critically, having received the lowest score among the 4 questions (Figure 6). The key questions is therefore: are we going to specifically teach critical thinking, and if yes, what is the best way to do it? As noted by Coles and Robinson (1989:

The problem is not whether we can teach thinking. The evidence suggests we can. The problem continues to be whether we are willing to make the pedagogic changes necessary to do so, and if we are, which changes might be the most effective. (p.20)

As reported by Cheah (2009), student learning is largely compartmentalized due to the largely modular nature of the teaching in the Polytechnic. Even though troubleshooting skills are taught in various modules, the application is largely confined to the topic within the module. Getting students to apply chemical engineering concepts learnt in different modules to solve a problem related to chemical plant operation will therefore pose a tremendous challenge to lecturers.

Morrison (2005) emphasized that an engineering curriculum is composed of two components: content and process, with the latter referring to the part of students' experience in their encounter with the materials and structure of a course. These two components should be integrated so as to bring together various subject contents that have been taught independently. One of the processes is of course critical thinking in problem solving. The way to resolve this dilemma, much like other engineering skills (including teamwork and communication) is to integrate critical thinking skills into more modules across the entire curriculum. Only by merging theory with practice (albeit a simulated one, as in this case) can students really internalize the theories learnt and appreciate the significance of what they were taught.

Future Plans

We believed that critical thinking in the context of this work is important enough to introduce similar activities into other modules. Woods, et al (2000) noted that people acquire skills most effectively through practice and feedback. No matter how many times students see a skill demonstrated, they rarely master it until they have attempted it repeatedly and received guidance in how to improve their performance after each attempt. As pointed out by Smith and Spurling (1999):

Critical thinking is a key lifelong learning skill, which must be developed in all parts of the learning scene.

The situation here in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering is that there is still no widespread usage of dynamic simulation tools despite the fact that such tools were made available more than 5 years ago. Often it is the interested staff who tried various approaches on their own in their respective modules, often without a consistent approach towards integrating the usage throughout the entire curriculum.

The use of these tools in any sort of uniform way and in a manner that deeply affects how content is delivered

and learning takes place is certainly non-existent. Such reluctance to embrace the technology was pointedly noted by Kulacki and Krueger (1998):

Despite the many papers presented at not only the world conferences but also at other learning educational conferences the use of computer-based instructional techniques is "spotty" at best.

This is echoed by Savelki et al (2002), who noted that chemical process simulation is currently underutilized in the chemical engineering curriculum, with heavy usage skewed towards plant design courses and equilibrium stage operations primarily with respect to multi-component distillation. These authors suggested that the use of process simulation be increased in other topics in chemical engineering.

The lack of widespread adoption of dynamic simulation can perhaps be attributed to the lack on concerted effort by the school management to promote their use. On the other hand, staff members typically cited lack of time, lack of familiarity with the tools, or lack of knowledge about other modules to effectively integrate activities using such tools into their modules.

There are many models in the EnVision package that are amenable for introduction into other chemical engineering modules such as *Process Instrumentation*, *Process Control*, *Rotating Equipment*, *Separation Processes*, etc. Activities can be designed to provide students with more opportunities to practice their critical thinking and troubleshooting skills.

To obtain more "buy-in" we would like to help other module coordinators by working closely with them to identify selected topics in their modules which are amenable to the introduction of dynamic simulation.

Already in the pipeline at the time of this paper is the plan on a 2-year study on students' ability to apply the critical thinking process – with the help of dynamic simulation – that they learnt in a Year-2 module on *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention* to a Year-3 module *Plant Design Project*. Effort will also be directed towards developing more in-depth assessment tools for evaluating effectiveness of using dynamic simulation in inculcating critical thinking among students.

The long-term benefit that we hoped to achieve is that the practice of critical thinking, in the manner defined in this work, will be prevalent in various modules throughout the Diploma in Chemical Engineering curriculum. This will tie in well with our effort to incorporate sustainable development into the curriculum. There is great similarity between the learning outcome that we strived to achieve via dynamic simulation and the demand on the practice of sustainability. As noted by the U.K. Higher Education Academy (HEA, 2006):

Some of the skills and knowledge necessary required for sustainable development include an appreciation of the inter-connectedness of environmental, social, political and economic aspects of sustainable development; understanding contested notions of sustainable development; problem solving skills; creative, holistic and critical thinking; self reflection; and bridging the gap between theory and practice.

It can be seen that the practice of sustainability, like understanding the inter-relationship between process variable in a chemical plant, also demanded that engineers be able to interpret the inter-relationship between variables, but in a much wider scale in both depth and breadth. Huntzinger, et al (2007) noted that:

By developing critical thinking in engineering students, the next generation of professionals may be more likely to give consideration to issues (e.g. the environment, social equity, biodiversity) that they otherwise would have ignored.

We therefore hope that students will be able to extend what they learnt in plant operations to sustainable development, especially in the context of chemical engineering education.

Conclusions

We have obtained encouraging results on students' perceived usefulness of dynamic simulation. We need to improve their ability to use critical thinking through more frequent practice. To this end, we will develop more exercises for integration into other modules. Furthermore to better evaluate the effectiveness of dynamic simulation in inculcating critical thinking, we will extend and refine our assessment and evaluation approaches as part of the research endeavour.

References

- Bell, J.T. & Fogler, H.S. (1997). The Application of Virtual Reality to Chemical Engineering Education. *Proceedings of the 1997 International Conference on Simulation in Engineering Education*, January 12-15, Simulation Series 29(2), Society for Computer Simulation, San Diego.
- Carroll, R.T. (2004). *Becoming a Critical Thinker: A Guide for the New Millennium*, 2nd Ed., Pearson Custom Publishing.
- Cheah, S.M. (2009), Using CDIO to Revamp the Chemical Engineering Curriculum, *Proceedings of the 5th International CDIO Conference*, June 7-10; Singapore.
- Coles, M.J. & Robinson, W.D. (1989). *Teaching Thinking: A Survey of Programmes in Education*. The Bristol Press.
- De Jong, T., & Van Joolingen, W. R. (1998). Scientific Discovery Learning with Computer Simulations of Conceptual Domains. *Review of Educational Research*, 68, 179-201.
- Eich-Sollner, E., Lory, P. Burr, P. & Kroner, A. (1997). Stationary and Dynamic Flowsheeting in the Chemical Engineering Industry, *Surv. Math. Ind.*, Vol.7 No.1.
- Felder, R.M. and Brent R. (2003). Designing and Teaching Courses to Satisfy the ABET Engineering Criteria. *J. of Engrg. Education*, 92 (1), 7-29.
- Gephardt, Z.O. (2005). Troubleshooting in The Engineering Curriculum. AICHE Annual Meeting, October 31; Cincinnati, Ohio, USA.
- Gossage, J.L., Yaws, C.L., Chen, D.H., Li K., Ho, T.C., Hopper J. & Cocke, D.L. (2001). Integrating Best Practice Pedagogy with Computer-aided Modeling and Simulation to Improve Undergraduate Chemical Engineering Education. *Proceedings of the 2001 American Society for Engineering Education Annual Conference & Exposition*. American Society for Engineering Education.
- Gurmen, N.H., Lucas J.J., Malmgren, R.D. & Fogler, H.S. (2003). Improving Critical Thinking and Creative Problem Solving Skills by Interactive Troubleshooting. *Proceedings of the 2003 American Society for Engineering Education Annual Conference & Exposition*, American Society for Engineering Education.
- HEA (2006). Sustainable Development in Higher Education - Current Practice and Future Development. The Higher Education Academy, UK.
- Hermann, A. (2002). Teaching Critical Thinking Online, *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, June.
- Huntzinger, D.N. Hutchins M.J. Gierke, J.S. & Sutherland J.W. (2007). Enabling Sustainable Thinking in Undergraduate Engineering Education, *Int. J. Engrg Ed.* Vol. 23, No. 2, pp. 218-230.
- Hyperion Systems Engineering (2006). *Dynamic Simulation and Chemical Engineering*. Retrieved from <http://www.hyperion.com.cy/EN/index.html>
- Jonassen D. (2001). Computers as Mindtools for Engaging Learners in Critical Thinking, *3rd International Symposium on Computers in Education*, Sep 26-28, Viseu, Portugal.
- Kulacki, F. A. & E. R. Krueger (1998). Trends in Engineering Education - An International Perspective, *Annual Meeting of the International Conference on Engineering Education*, August 17-20; Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.
- Luyben, W.L. (2002). *Plant-wide Dynamic Simulators in Chemical Processing and Control*. CRC.

Morrison, F.A. (2005). Drawing the Connections between Engineering Science and Engineering Practice, *Chemical Engineering Education*, Vol.39, No.2, pp.110-115,

Moore, D.T. (2006). Critical Thinking and Intelligence Analysis. *Joint Military Intelligence College, Occasional Paper 14*, May 2006, pg. 2.

Savelski, M.J., Dahm, K.D. & Hesketh, R.P. (2002). Is Process Simulation Effectively Utilized in Chemical Engineering Courses. *Chemical Engineering Education*, Vol.36, No.3, p192-97 Sum 2002

Smith, J. & Spurling, A. (1999). *Lifelong Learning: Riding the Tiger*. London: Cassell.

Willingham, D.T. (2007). Critical Thinking – Why is it So Hard to Teach? *American Educator*, Summer Issue.

Womack, J.W. (1986). Dynamic Simulation in the Processing Industries: Case Studies from Mobil Experience. *Modeling, Identification and Control*, Vol.6 No.4, 201-216.

Woods, D.R., Felder, R.M., Rugarcia A. & Stice, J.E. (2000). The Future of Engineering Education. III. Developing Critical Skills, *Chemical Engineering Education*, Vol. 34, No. 2, pp. 108–117.